

**Dissemination and
Communication Plan**
**WP6 Enabling environment and
awareness raising**

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Executive Summary

The purpose of this document (D6.1) is to set the dissemination and communication strategy that will be followed and elaborate on the project's dissemination and communication activities that will be executed throughout the duration of the project. The strategy, activities and tools which the DIANA project will use to disseminate the project results and to communicate with the wider public are outlined in the following parts.

It should be noted that DIANA is an innovation action, which means that the dissemination and communication strategy should be set in a way that will also take into consideration the commercialisation of the results. Within that framework, even though the brand identity development will start from an early stage, the identity of the final commercial product that will result from the project activities may be modified and launched under a new name.

For clarity it is essential to distinguish dissemination and communication activities:

- 💧 According to the definition given by the European Commission “Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium. It is a process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups (like research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers) in a targeted way, to enable them to use the results in their own work. This process must be planned and organised at the beginning of each project, usually in a dissemination plan”¹.
- 💧 Again according to the European Commission “Communication means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges”².

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/faqs/faq-933.html>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/faqs/faq-933.html>

D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan

In the following parts we are going to describe the context of the DIANA project, the strategy that is going to be followed (methodology, objectives, expected results), the target groups and audiences, the dissemination and communication tools that the consortium is going to use, as well as some of the foreseen actions that will be taken during and after the end of the project, the role of the project partners, the monitoring and evaluation of the plan and finally the schedule and action planning.

1. Context

Agriculture accounts for approximately a quarter of the 182 billion m³ of water extracted every year in Europe. This substantial amount of abstracted EU water is used predominantly for irrigation since it is a common practice in agriculture aimed at improving crop productivity, reducing risks of crop failures due to dry periods and stabilising yields. At the same time, however, irrigation is also a major cause of non-authorized water (over-)abstraction, or in other words the abstraction of larger volumes of water than officially permitted and/or sustainably available, thus imposing increasing pressures on the sustainability of European water resources. With this in mind and given the scarcity of our water resources as well as the fact that drought is becoming an increasingly frequent phenomenon across Europe³, it is evident that novel and innovative solutions are required in order to address these threatening problems that EU waters are currently facing. In this respect, the latest advances in Earth Observation (EO) pose an unprecedented opportunity to develop commercial services for EU water authorities to control and deal with these problems in a cost-effective and systematic manner.

It is quite surprising that the only method that is currently being used to detect and monitor non-authorized water abstractions is through the traditional time-consuming and costly field inspections carried out by experienced professionals in correlation with existing water rights databases and more often than not on a random basis. However, this method incorporates significant costs, it is hindered by the limited availability of human and financial resources required for carrying out extensive inspections, is not possible to achieve given the number of users and the difficulty to access private properties and to detect tampering or maintenance problems.

The overarching objective of DIANA is to co-create, co-design and demonstrate in real operational environments a commercial service platform that will empower water management authorities to optimise the identification and inspection of non-authorized water abstractions for irrigation as well as significantly improve the monitoring and assessment of their water management policies and practices, both in standard and special conditions such as in cases of drought. DIANA

³ Droughts are long term imbalance resulting from water demand exceeding available water resources and may occur anywhere in Europe including high as well as low rainfall areas regardless of seasons.

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will leverage Earth Observation (EO) data as well as state-of-the-art models for the identification of (illegally) irrigated areas and the estimation of abstracted water volumes in order to offer a demand-driven suite of data products and services, that will be affordable, cost-effective and of high value added, mainly but not exclusively, due to the:

- Enhanced temporal and spatial resolution of the Sentinel satellites which provide EO data on a free, open and full access basis, therefore enabling us to drastically reduce service costs by avoiding the use of expensive commercial satellite imagery, while achieving large geographic coverage with great accuracy.
- Systemisation and optimisation of monitoring and inspections achieved by continuous monitoring and better guiding field inspections to areas where infringements are more likely to be taking place, thus greatly increasing the efficiency and decreasing the costs of mapping and monitoring irrigated areas, freeing a considerable portion of the already scarce human and financial resources of public authorities to be directed towards other activities.
- Minimisation of the in-house resources, infrastructure and skills required for effectively employing EO data to manage their water resources more sustainably, as DIANA customers will not have to purchase and install any additional equipment or have any special technical/informatics background to benefit from the provided services.

DIANA services will apply to different types of non-authorized water abstractions including (i) abstractions of water aimed at irrigating areas without official water rights as well as (ii) water abstractions beyond the volumes allowed by relevant authorities (either constant or during periods of special restrictions). Moreover, they will cover a multitude of suitable agricultural and operational contexts (e.g. in terms of types of irrigated crops, climate conditions, target area size, administrative, technical and financial capabilities of users, etc.). In addition, DIANA users will be able to leverage our value propositions in order to produce meaningful information for farmers (e.g. drought forecasts for crop planning and selection), enabling us to promote further socio-economic and environmental benefits to the European economy and society as a whole.

2. Strategy

The key aim for dissemination strategies is to transmit useful and useable knowledge to appropriate target audiences, including research communities, practitioners, the public, policy makers and regulatory bodies. Each of these target audiences has its own particular needs, creating the need for tailored and specific dissemination strategies. A dissemination strategy is an evolving plan that aims to:

- extract clear, simple, and active main messages or key implications from research results;
- identify credible 'carriers' of the message;
- pinpoint key decision-maker audiences for the messages; and
- pinpoint key decision-maker audiences for the messages

All in all the key questions that need to be answered when creating the dissemination plan are: a) what is the impact wished (context and objectives of the project); b) who is it addressed to (target audiences); c) what is the most effective way to reach that audience (tools); and d) when and by who will an action be executed in order to achieve the above (activities)? Such an approach relies on a solid understanding of the target audiences and the objectives of the communications aimed at them, as well as the best possible use of the channels and tools available.

2.1. Methodology

The characteristics of the most effective dissemination strategies are the following⁴:

- **Are Audience-Oriented:** Ultimately, research dissemination is communication, and different audiences require different approaches. Good communication considers the practical needs, current knowledge level, and language/terminology preferences of the audience;

⁴<https://www.american.edu/provost/grad/upload/Dissemination-Toolkit.pdf>

- 💧 **Focus on Goals:** The dissemination should reflect the purpose of the research project, whether it be to inform, to motivate, or otherwise. Rather than simply reporting what the research uncovered, contextualize the information to help the audience understand why the research was done, what makes the results important, and what actions should be taken next in light of the research findings;
- 💧 **Are Selectively Chosen and Combined:** There are a wide variety of ways to share knowledge, and not all will be suitable for a given project. Identify the dissemination tools that are likely to promote the goals of the research project. If there is a broad target audience for the research, a combination of strategies might be used: an article in a community newsletter could reach local citizens, a website can be shared with organizations around the country, a formal report can be sent to political decision makers;
- 💧 **Are Accessible:** Consider what can be done to make the information available to those who have particular needs or who face barriers to access. For example, when planning a dissemination event, consider the venue's accessibility, the day and time of the event, whether childcare or transportation may be needed, whether an interpreter should be used, etc. Similarly, written materials should be available in a form and language that can be understood by the research's audience. Other accessibility issues may arise in relation to specific projects (for example, a website should be accessible to those who use text readers, videos should be closed-captioned, and so on);
- 💧 **Make the Best Use of Available Resources:** Collaborative research projects have the benefit of involving individuals from more than one organization, allowing access to a diversity of skills, networks, and resources. Research partners can take advantage of formal resources (e.g., organization coordinators may share research at community meetings or conferences, or university partners may use U of R's External Relations channels to publicize the project), but consider informal opportunities as well: for example, community partners may have relationships with other organizations that could support the dissemination effort, or faculty advisors may know other instructors who could incorporate the research report into their classes.
- 💧 **Allow for Two-Way Communication:** Research indicates that dissemination strategies that result in new ideas and actions being implemented tend to be based on relationships and dialogue, rather than a one-way flow of information. To encourage the target audience to understand and use the research, find ways to build a dialogue to explore

how the research can be useful to specific audiences.

- 💧 **Are Clear and Focused:** All project documents should: a) be concise and to the point; b) highlight the key research findings and recommendations; c) define any specialist terminology used; d) be presented in an attractive, readable format (use a clear, standard-size or large font and headings to organize the information); e) except in certain very formal cases, include images, graphs, or bullet points to break up lengthy blocks of text.

In other words the key for a successful dissemination strategy is the application of a common framework, providing the consortium with a common process and a set of common criteria, with the purpose to identify, monitor and select the suited dissemination channels. In the following parts we are going to examine that process and criteria (project logo, website, deliverable templates, press releases, newsletters and printable promotional material (leaflet, brochure, posters etc), as well as the various channels that will be used (social media and networking groups, mass media, local news, Network of Interest, scientific publications and participation in relevant events).

Finally, it should be underlined that another important parameter for the success of a dissemination plan is the direct involvement of all the partners of the consortium in the processes, especially the ones responsible for pilot implementation. All project partners must feel a sense of ownership of the project and must be involved at all stages of the strategy's development. It must be ensured that each consortium member has responsibility for a particular aspect of the strategy's implementation, but also a shared vision and common understanding of what has to be disseminated together with a way of describing this to the audiences outside of the project and who may benefit from the project work.

2.2. Main assets to be disseminated

Some of DIANA assets that can be disseminated and/or exploited later on is provided below:

- 💧 DIANA data products and services aimed at enabling water management authorities to systematically and efficiently detect and estimate the level of non-authorized water abstractions for irrigation, pro-actively plan for and manage their water resources in drought conditions as well as better implement the WFD;

- DIANA service platform and its components including the web and mobile applications, the GIS dashboard and the REST API to be employed by all DIANA applications and modules for information retrieval and storage;
- Novel knowledge to be generated through the implementation of the project with respect to the application of EO derived data and technologies for identifying and estimating the amounts of irrigation water abstracted without authorisation in different operational, administrative, cultural and legal contexts across the EU;
- Data to be collected and produced in the frame of DIANA activities (e.g. EO-based, satellite, meteorological and ancillary data as well as data derived from the identification of the user requirements, the co-creation workshops, the evaluation and validation activities, etc.)

2.3. Objectives

The core objective of DIANA Dissemination and Communication strategy is to fulfil the need to disseminate the concept, methodologies, pilots and outcomes of the project to particular community or communities, but also the wider public. Below we are listing the main objectives underpinning the DIANA strategy, in brief:

- Raise awareness and provide high visibility of the project and later on of the product, among the target groups;
- Establish a strong brand identity from the beginning;
- Encourage involvement of other stakeholders;
- Raise awareness of policy makers and public bodies;
- Facilitate synergies with similar or complementary initiatives and;
- Promote, implement and spread the use of the service.

The expected results of the dissemination and communication strategy are: raising awareness; identification of target groups and how they can exploit project results; and promotion of active participation in the project.

3. Target groups and audiences

The present part identifies the main target groups and audiences to which DIANA results will be addressed towards. It is of the outmost importance to identify the target groups, since that will enable the consortium to decide where and how to market DIANA in an effective and less costly way. Furthermore, segmenting the market will help in identifying the similarities between the different target groups, as well as their differences, in order to better understand them and make the service and/or product more appealing and interesting to them.

In the table below we present the different target groups of DIANA and we also include a wider audience segment to which the action itself and its results will be communicated:

Target group	Activity of target group	Example
Water managers	Responsible for monitoring and inspecting abstractions of water for irrigation	Public authorities or associations of irrigators depending on national/regional particularities
Authorities	Responsible for developing and implementing water/drought management plans and/or the WDF as well as issue irrigation water rights	River basin authorities, regional or local authorities
Farmers, agricultural cooperatives and consultancies	Active in the agricultural sector	Agribusiness professionals, advisors, innovation intermediaries
Research and Academia	Also with activities relevant to the agricultural sector	Academic institutions, non-university public research organisations, research and technology organisations
Non-governmental organisations and civic society groups	Interested in sustainable water management in the EU and aimed at addressing relevant social challenges and needs	Associations and NGOs
Other Stakeholders	That may be interested in project outcomes	Repolicy and decision makers at EU level, etc
Wider public	People that have an interest on the issue	People that have an interest on the issue

Table 1 Target groups and audiences

All dissemination activities will be in line with the protection of IPR as well as the confidentiality obligations, which were established in the Consortium Agreement (CA). All partners will actively engage in the dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities that will be appropriately conducted along the lifespan of the project and beyond.

4. Dissemination and communication tools

The following sections describe the dissemination tools that will be used within the context of the DIANA dissemination strategy. These tools can be further specified after consultation with local partners and in relevance to the specified priorities on local level.

4.1. Visual identity

The Business Dictionary defines the visual identity as follows: “Visible elements of a brand, such as colour, form, and shape, which encapsulate and convey the symbolic meanings that cannot be imparted through words alone⁵”. In other words a message can be conveyed not only through words, but also through other means such as images, colours, shapes. Within that framework a brand identity was created for DIANA during months one and two of the project that took into account the following:

- An appropriate aesthetic that can be identified with the project objectives;
- The message that needs to be conveyed in targeted and mass audiences and;
- A brand that could translate easily to the different dissemination channels (printed material, web, mobile etc).

In the following parts we are examining the different components that comprise the visual identity of DIANA project and next the different tools in which that aesthetic is captured.

It should be noted here that across all outputs of the DIANA project a text concerning the source of the project’s funding and disclosing the Grant Agreement number will be provided, along with the European flag (as specified in European Commission, 2012).

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⁵ <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/visual-identity.html>

4.2. Logo and colour palette

The logo is one of the most important aspects of the visual identity of a product and/or a project. It is the major graphical representation of the project and its' results and becomes one of the most seen elements of the visual identity during the dissemination and communication activities. Below we can see the logo of DIANA:

A first look of the DIANA logo helps the interested party to recognize the water droplet, which is directly related to water in all its' facets. However, with a second more extensive look the interested party can also recognise an "all seeing eye", which is directly connected with what people see, but also what technological advances helps them to "see". In combination those two elements of the logo along with the colour palate comprise the project's logo.

The colours that were selected were the blue of the water, but of the sky as well (where satellites that provide the Earth Observation Data are), while the black circle with the white one outside stand for the colour if they eye. Below we can see the exact colours that were used for the logo:

Blue Accent 94,177,229
Black 0,0,0
White-255,255,255
Grey Accent 3 80% Lighter 237,237,237

The purpose of the DIANA logo is fully aligned with the project's objective to use earth observation data in order to identify and inspect the non-authorized water abstractions for irrigation.

4.3 Templates

Based on the visual identity established by the logo and the colour pallet, templates were produced for text documents (Microsoft Word) and presentations (Microsoft PowerPoint). Templates were produced for the following types of documents:

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- 🔹 Deliverable documents;
- 🔹 Non-Deliverable Documents, such as memos, notes or letters;
- 🔹 Deliverable document reviews;
- 🔹 Event reports;
- 🔹 Press releases;
- 🔹 Presentations.

Samples of each template are supplied in the figures below.

Figure 1 Deliverable Template

Figure 2 Non- Deliverable Document Template

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Figure 3 Reviewer Template

Figure 4 Press Release Template

Figure 5 Event Reporting Template

Figure 6 Presentation (Ppt) Template

4.4 Website

The DIANA website (to be released at M4) will initially take the form of a web presence focused on the project. The site will both be used as a management tool among the project partners by offering access to all documentation and deliverables produced in the course of the project and contain the basic information about the project (structure, objectives, concept, team, etc.) in order to be used as a dissemination tool that will assist partners in reaching stakeholders, as well as the wider audience.

Within that framework the structure of the project will be kept simple and straightforward, in an attempt to make it easy to understand and use by the potential users and stakeholders. Furthermore, the site will be available in all languages of the partners that are participating in the consortium: Greek, Spanish, Italian, Romanian, and French for ease of uptake from the local communities to which the partners will disseminate it.

The website will be updated and upgraded during the whole duration of the project. More specifically, both the structure and the content will be modified to depict the progress of the project: additional sections, news, graphic material and other info will be constantly uploaded. Website activity will be monitored using Google analytics, a tool that helps to analyse visitor traffic and gives a complete picture of the website audience and their needs. Google analytics will be used in order to improve website quality and to evaluate the website use as a dissemination tool.

4.4.1 Email account and email lists

For the needs of official communication, an email account of DIANA project will be established. The address will be info@diana-h2020.eu and/or info@diana-project.eu. This account will be included in all used dissemination tools, such as the project website, social media accounts, printed material etc. AgroApps, as the coordinator of the project, will be responsible managing of this account, while enquiries, comments, and information will be forwarded by AgroApps to project partners if necessary.

In addition, several mailing lists will be established for associate partners, stakeholders, for those with other broad interests in the project, and for potential DIANA output users. These mailing lists are accessible via the DIANA website for self-registration. Opportunities to participate, project updates and an electronic copy of the newsletter, will be sent out to these lists to maintain contact with the community throughout the project. Also each partner is encouraged to develop and maintain an email list related to the partner's country of origin and field of interest.

The mailing lists will be managed by AgroApps PC, using MailChimp application. MailChimp was selected since it offers plenty advanced reporting options that can be accessed from anywhere. Materials to be distributed to these lists should be sent to AgroApps PC. The sign up form for all of the mailing lists, including DIANA Newsletter, will be accessed at the homepage of DIANA website.

4.5 Social Media

The DIANA project will establish a social media presence during month three (M3) of the project (D6.4 Social Media Accounts) using the services of Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Youtube for the following reasons:

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- As of the fourth quarter of 2016, Facebook had 1.86 billion monthly active users. Facebook has the audience to help you promote your business and attract new people to your site. With so many registered users Facebook is a top notch tool to help DIANA reach a wider audience and through that even more specific target groups (such as the Global Water Partnership).
- Twitter is characterized as a microblogging service. As of the fourth quarter of 2016 that microblogging service averaged at 319 million monthly active users. At the beginning of 2016, Twitter had reached 310 MAU per quarter. Twitter users are able to read tweets, meaning posts that have the limitation of one hundred and forty characters, so in other words every message has to be clear and to the point. It's a great way of joining or even starting discussions with influencers and industry experts to raise the profile of your business and build valuable connections.
- During the most recently reported quarter, LinkedIn had 467 million users, up from 450 million users in the previous one. LinkedIn is a networking site that allows members to create profiles and make connections with others as a way of establishing professional relationships. The site is available in over 200 countries worldwide in 20 different languages.
- YouTube is a video sharing website that allows users to upload, view, rate, share, add to favorites, report and comment on videos. Both private individuals and large production companies have used YouTube to grow audiences. According to the website itself "YouTube has over a billion users—almost a third of all people on the Internet—and every day, people watch hundreds of millions of hours of YouTube videos and generate billions of views⁶". DIANA can leverage the opportunity that YouTube has to offer and share webinars, power point presentations, or internal and external interviews that will drive traffic to the channel and potential customers and/or the wider public learning about DIANA.

Anyone will be able to follow the media accounts of DIANA project. All accounts will include a brief description of the project (name, objectives, etc) which will be added as an additional source of information available for the general public. The links of the different social media accounts

⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/yt/press/en-GB/statistics.html>

will also be displayed in the project's website, while (where this is an option) the link from the website will be displayed in the social media accounts.

The website, will remain the project's primary online source for information. Social media will be used to complement the website's information and broaden the reach of messages through multiple channels. No confidential information will be posted to any social media under any circumstances. Comments containing any of the following shall not be allowed and will be removed by social media accounts managers:

- Comments not topically related to the particular site or article being commented on. Profane language or content.
- Content that promotes, fosters or perpetuates discrimination on the basis of race, creed, colour, age, religion, gender, marital status, status with regard to public assistance, national origin, physical or mental disability, or sexual orientation.
- Sexual content or links to sexual content.
- Conduct or encouragement of illegal activity. Content related to advertising or promotions.
- Information that may tend to compromise the safety or security of the public or public systems.
- Content that violates a legal ownership interest of any other party.

4.6 Printable material

4.6.1 Leaflet

Leaflets are a simple means of informing the different audiences of the purpose, progress or findings of the project. Leaflets can address general project issues since they will be printable in-house and will allow a fast replication. Leaflets will be editable and printable by any of the project partners, and therefore, will be tailorable both in terms of content and language. In order to raise awareness of the project even at the initial stage, the consortium has created a first version of a leaflet to be distributed through all partners to any dissemination event they participate in. The paper size of the leaflet will be A5 and special folding and cutting will be applied. For the initial needs of the project 1000 leaflets will be printed. They will also be available for download from the project website. However, pilot partners are strongly encouraged to translate the leaflet in their language and distribute it to the pilot sites in order to maximise engagement. The leaflet will

be circulated by email or printed and distributed at events. The initial version of the DIANA leaflet will be circulated in month three of the project (D6.3 Promotional Material).

4.6.2 Brochure

The project brochure will be one of the main promotional materials of the project, to be delivered and sent to the various stakeholders, allowing a fast understanding of the project's aims, activities, pilots and expected results. The brochure will be in A4 size and will have multiple pages. It is a more official document and will contain more information and graphics than the leaflet.

4.6.3 Poster

Posters are dissemination means that are mainly used in events that can be either organised by the project or can be external conferences, symposia, workshops, seminars or others in relevant domains. Such posters will be provided as necessary. An initial poster will be created that will include the following main items:

- DIANA Logo – Slogan – Key Words,
- EU emblem and statement of the EC funding
- One paragraph description
- Tag line – Key message

The initial version of the DIANA poster will be circulated among partners in month three (M3) of the project (D6.3 Promotional Material).

4.6.4 Info fact sheet

The info factsheet will be a single sheet printed A4 (one or two sided depending on the amount of text) paper containing information on the project as a whole, but also can contain and analyse specific parts of the project e.g a Work Package fact sheet or a factsheet dedicated to serve a specific audience. The main difference with the leaflet is the layout. Different fact sheets will be produced during the course of the project and will be available in the website. The factsheet will be disseminated in formal events (e.g. workshops, conferences, etc.) in order to inform all relevant stakeholders about the key points of the DIANA project. The factsheet

will be also available in an online version through the DIANA website. An initial version of the DIANA factsheet is available in ANNEX I.

4.6.5 Press kit

The media kit is a pre-packaged set of promotional material of the project for the purpose to be distributed in the members of the press and media. Media kit is not a distinctive dissemination material itself. For DIANA it will include a conference folder, a leaflet, a factsheet, the latest newsletter and a USB stick.

4.7 Key Messages

Key messages can help you prioritize and crystallize information, while ensuring consistency, continuity and accuracy. Key messages can help you stay focused when speaking with media or stakeholders. Especially when used on a repetitive basis such messages can act as the foundation of a dissemination and communication strategy in all written, as well as spoken communications. Key messages can in just a few simple words:

- Act as an elevated, one sentence pitch;
- Engage the audience that you wish;
- Capture in a nutshell: what you do, what you stand for and the value that you have.

A successful key message you needs to be: a) concise; b) strategic; c) relevant; d) compelling; e) simple; f) memorable; g) real; and h) tailored.

A pull of key messages will be created for DIANA from months 3 (along with the promotional material) to 12 (when the second version of the dissemination and communication deliverable will be submitted) based on the needs that will be identified by the partners. All partners will be able to use those different messages to better address the different dissemination and communication needs.

5. Dissemination and communication actions

The following sections outline the dissemination activities envisioned to be carried out in the scope of the DIANA project. Before examining those, we are briefly presenting below the various project and dissemination interrelated activities.

Project phase	Project Actions	Dissemination actions
1st to 2nd year	Assess project characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Branding (logos, templates, etc) • Email lists and discussion forums and • Social networking tools
	Prepare deliverables ensuring that they are adaptable and finding can be easily found	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Printable material • Online repositories and other audio-visual material
	Articulate the value of the project outcomes and build credibility and familiarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participatory dissemination (partners) • Investigate for conferences, workshops, showcases of interest
	Identify potential adopters, assess their characteristics and identify other possible enablers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networks and communities of practice • Email lists and discussion forums • Social networking tools • Meetings and discussions (mainly internal) roundtables and invited presentations (from external members: i.e. advisory board)
	Plan for interaction and response to changes and opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networks and communities of practice • Email lists and discussion forums • Outline of newsletter
2nd to 3rd year	Support initial uptake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting and discussions with stakeholders from the pilot (and possibly other interested) areas • Presentations in workshops, events, conferences • Guides and material
	Support adoption and evaluation of the outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Influencing policy • Networks and communities of practice • Media releases
Post project	Expand to different potential adopters outside the initial target group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journal articles and book chapters • Project final report • Webpages, online repositories, audio-visual material and other online content • Media releases

Table 2 Interrelated project and dissemination activities

In the following parts we examine all relevant activities in depth.

5.1 Network of interest

The establishment and management of a Network of Interest (NoI) will be an ongoing activity during the entire life of the project, as well as after the end of the project. The aim of the establishment of a Network of Interest is to act as a main dissemination pole for the engagement of the DIANA target groups.

A network of interested parties in the field (i.e. farmers, rural associations, SMEs, etc.) will be created around the project so as to focus our dissemination activities to those on which they might have maximum effect. This dissemination activity will be an absolute priority. The idea behind the NoI is to exchange information, ideas and thoughts about the DIANA project, its goals, interests, objectives and business processes. An initial contact list containing contact information of potential members of the DIANA Network of Interest has been prepared.

These individuals are expected to be interested in the results of DIANA and, therefore, the DIANA consortium will try to keep them up to date about the project progress and will encourage them to participate in technical/scientific discussions generated by the consortium.

The DIANA NoI will provide the necessary knowledge to the project partners in order to disseminate the project objectives on local, regional, national and European level. A project User Group will be established early in the project, encompassing organizations of all relevant stakeholders. Our aim is to limit the interested participants to those that have the intention and the potential to utilize the DIANA solution and its future customers' base. All participants will be encouraged to be involved in discussions concerning technical and scientific issues of the project through the official DIANA website, and they will be invited to participate in the project policy workshops.

5.2 Mass media communication

Obtaining news coverage, whether at a national or local level, can increase the profile of the project at a great extent and reach a very wide body of people. The main target is journalists, related TV/radio shows, columns in newspapers.

The scope of the mass media communication activities will be to inform the general public through mass media about the DIANA project, to obtain news coverage at a national or local level, in order to increase the profile of the project and reach a very wide body of people. These activities will target a wide variety of news agencies and mass media with general or specialised interests, individual journalists with a special interest DIANA related topics, related TV/radio shows or columns in newspapers. The DIANA consortium intends to disseminate the DIANA project through TV and radio channels, web media, and newspapers and magazines - either printed or electronic ones.

Mass media will be fed through the following dissemination tools:

- press releases
- audiovisual material that will be uploaded at YouTube channel
- project results and newsfeed that will be available at the project's website
- audiovisual or printed material with information about the DIANA meetings
- project's presentations and partners' interviews that could be performed during the organisation of targeted events or participation in non-project events.

The DIANA partners are encouraged to disseminate the DIANA project through mass media on a regular basis. However, the official contact with the mass media will be held by Zeco through the official email account of the DIANA project.

5.3 Scientific publications

It is expected that the DIANA project will result in a number of publications in scientific, peer-reviewed journals. Project partners are encouraged to collaborate with each other and jointly prepare publications relevant to the DIANA project. Scientific journals that provide open access (OA) to all their publications will be preferred, as it is required by the European Commission.

In specific, as it is required in DIANA Grand Agreement article 29.2 "each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must: a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications. Moreover, the

beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications, b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest: (i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or (ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case, and finally c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms "European Union (EU)" and "Horizon 2020"
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

5.4 Participation in events

A common way to achieve an effective dissemination is the participation of project partners in targeted non-project events where project as whole or specific actions and results of it can be presented. These events can include scientific conferences and symposiums, workshops and other open events relevant to the project objectives. By participating in such events, project partners will be able to promote project activities and outputs beyond partnership and involved territories. However, prior to any participation in targeted non-project events, project partners must notify the project coordinator (AgroApps) and partner 2eco responsible for dissemination. This notification process is compulsory for dissemination monitoring and evaluation purposes. Additionally a specific template for participating in events for reporting purposes.

It should be noted that scientific conferences and symposiums are key venues to present new scientific knowledge and methodologies emerging from DIANA project. Partners' representatives are encouraged to participate in major conferences of relevant fields presenting the DIANA project and related scientific results. If a poster is included in the participation, it must follow the poster template of the project and other visibility guidelines related to source of funding. A detailed list of conferences and symposiums relevant to DIANA project is available in ANNEX II –

Targeted external non-project events. The list will be updated with new conferences and symposiums during the whole duration of the project.

Furthermore, DIANA project partners are encouraged to participate in key workshops in the fields of irrigation, agriculture, precision agriculture, Earth Observation throughout the duration of the project in order to increase the project's visibility and build the DIANA contact list and the Network of Interest. Furthermore, other Open Events such as Agricultural Fairs with a focus on new technologies and irrigation or Shows with similar subjects will be also useful means to disseminate the DIANA project in different target audiences than those attended workshops.

All partners are encouraged to inform partner AgroApps about such events to be held in their region or elsewhere. A detailed list of workshops and other Open events relevant to DIANA project is available in ANNEX II – Targeted external non-project events. The list will be updated during the course of the project.

5.5 Informal networking

Networking will be performed through the participation in relevant events linked to the project theme, operating by all project partners throughout the duration of the project. This will be coupled by informal person-to-person meetings with relevant stakeholders. These are additional activities to the project events organized in DIANA for dissemination (i.e. project workshops) and other purposes (i.e. co-creation workshops among others).

5.6 DIANA engagement events and final event

As mentioned in the description of work, a valuable measure for dissemination and knowledge exchange will be a series of six stakeholder engagement events to be organised by project partners at the regions where the pilots will take place with a view to interact with and mobilise regional/national stakeholder communities. As such, these stakeholder engagement events will be hosted in Spain (two events organised by AGRISAT), in Romania (two events organised by ROSA) and in Italy (two events organised by SANNIO ALIFANO). The events will be organised from month 16 of the project and on, due to the fact that pilots are more actively involved in the project after that month. After month sixteen AgriSat, ROSA and Sannio Alifanio will provide the

Coordinator with the possible dates for realizing the events in the different points of interest. Furthermore, until month sixteen partners will have at their disposal various dissemination material to use for participants and they can always require further material if they recognize the need and ask from dissemination partner Zeco in a timely manner.

Apart from the stakeholder engagement events a Final Dissemination event (to be organised by Zeco possibly as a satellite event at a larger international event in Brussels) we will be able to present the results of the project as well as the value proposition of our platform and its service offering at an international audience, setting the stage for its market uptake after the project completion.

During the final event partners will have the opportunity to capitalise on the network of interest that they have built during the three years of DIANA project, as well as other target audiences that they have attracted, using the various dissemination tools, to present the outcome of the project and the finalised platform that will be ready for uptake.

The aim of the final event will be to present the efforts that were made the previous years and showcase the benefits of the final platform and services, as tested and validated by the final users in the pilot areas.

5.7 Advisory Board

The Advisory Board is an integral part of DIANA project. It will be set up and operated in order to act as a consultation body to DIANA that will share its knowledge and expertise with us in key stages of project implementation. Within that framework the Advisory Board will also act as an additional dissemination channel, promoting the project results, helping to identify and better understand key target groups, as well as reach them and finally it can help in the creation and development of the Network of Interest. Being a part of the sector and being respectable in their fields, the members of the Advisory Board can well help in that last aspect.

6. Partners' role in dissemination

The DIANA consortium consists of partners with significant links with stakeholders that have potential interest to the project and with experience in disseminating similar activities. All project partners are in a strong position to develop an effective “personal” dissemination strategy, building on key existing channels. These channels and links will provide direct access to the target groups and will act as core channels that will support the project’s sustainability and its effective exit strategy. The responsibilities of each project partner for the dissemination of DIANA, they are summarized in the following table:

Partner	Role in dissemination
2eco	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor and evaluate the dissemination activities; • Prepare the project logo; • Develop the project website; • Produce all printed material; • Organise project events; • Establish and manage the Network of Interest
AgroApps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate effectiveness of dissemination; • Make corrections and suggestions where needed; • Decide upon participation in external events; • Evaluate scientific publications;
AgriSat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply the dissemination strategy in pilot countries in co-operation with the local partners
Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disseminate the results to the public and to target groups related to their area of expertise; • Apply and advance the dissemination strategy in their country; • Participate and present the project in events organised by third parties; • Feed information to website and social media; • Publish articles, translate and develop informational material; • Suggest contacts for the project mailing list and the Network of Interest; • Provide performance data to the WP6 leader 2eco

Table 3 Partners' role in dissemination

7. Monitoring and evaluation

To ensure accurate monitoring and reporting of dissemination activities, DIANA deliverables include a number of reports linked to dissemination activities. The WP6 leader will be responsible for drafting the content of these reports, in collaboration with Project coordinator AgroApps and co-coordinator AgriSat. The following sections outline the DIANA reporting schedule, as well as the requirements for individual partners to provide information on their own dissemination activities.

Month in the Project	Deliverable Number and Title
M2, M12	D6.1 Dissemination and Communication plan
M18, M30	D6.5 Report on results of dissemination activities
M3	D6.2 Promotional Material
M3	D6.3 Social Media accounts
M4	D6.4 DIANA Web portal
M24	D6.6 Legal and institutional requirements report
M28	D6.7 Briefs for policy makers and water managers

Table 4 Deliverables of WP6

The leader of WP6 will be in charge of the overall monitoring of all dissemination activities and will report to the project coordinator in case of any problem. However, each partner is responsible for liaising with national and local media for dissemination purposes, and for ensuring that they engage enough stakeholders to properly enlarge the community.

For the reporting purposes of the specific work package the Event Report and Press Release templates can be used for the respective activities, while the non-deliverable template can be used for reporting all other dissemination activities, i.e. scientific publications, network of interest and informal communications with stakeholders and target audiences outside the consortium. All relevant templates can be found in the present document, Chapter 4 “Dissemination and communication tools”, Subchapter 4.4 “Templates”.

For the evaluation of the dissemination activities, a specific evaluation procedure will measure the impact of the activities. Each activity will be given a specific indicator which will be measured against a specific target value that will be set for the duration of the project. Below we are presenting in a table the impact indicators per activity, the target value that is set for the project and the means of verification for each indicator.

Performance Indicator	Target Value	Means of verification
Visitors to the project website	6.000	Google analytics
“Likes” on DIANA Facebook page	500	Facebook account data
Followers of DIANA on Twitter	300	Twitter account data
Members on LinkedIn group	200	LinkedIn account data
Number of viewers of audiovisual material on Youtube	1000	Number of views on Youtube
Publications on mass media	45	Dissemination reporting
Scientific publications	5	Dissemination reporting
Events to be attended by Project partners	10	Dissemination reporting
Newsletters produced	12	Copies available from reporting or via website
Number of subscribers to the newsletter	300	List of recipients
Number of contacts established in the Nol	200	List of stakeholders
Number of distributed printed material	2000	Dissemination reporting

Table 5 Impact indicators

8. Action planning (six months)

The dissemination activities that are going to be executed during the first six months of the project are presented below:

Activities	Month	1	2	3	4	5	6
D6.1 Dissemination and communication plan							
Research on dissemination and communication strategies to be followed							
Define target audiences							
Define dissemination tools							
Define role of partners							
D6.3 Promotional material							
Create visual identity							
Create templates (deliverable, non-deliverable, etc)							
Create poster							
Create leaflet and brochure							
D6.4 Social Media accounts							
Decide on the channels that are going to be used							
Create accounts							
Start uploading content							
D6.5 DIANA web portal							
Decide on layout and structure of the website							
Decide on content of website							
Upload content							
Link site with social media							
Create DIANA mailing list							

Table 6 Indicative action panning for first six months of project

13. Conclusion

In the present deliverable we have examined the Dissemination and Communication strategy that DIANA consortium is going to follow as a whole. We have described the different channels and tools that are going to be used, as well as the anticipated activities for the next six months. Due to the fact that this is a living document and that the project is very early on the implementation phase, many things mentioned here may be revised, adjusted and/or changed, based on the conclusions that we will draw from the activities and their results in the first six months. That will also be shown in the next deliverable for Communication and Dissemination Plan, D6.2.

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Annex I: Fact Sheet

Fact Sheet

Detection and Integrated Assessment of Non-authorized water Abstractions using EO

Concept

DIANA will create a commercial service platform specifically for water managing authorities; **DIANA** will empower them: a) to optimise identification and inspection of non-authorized water abstractions for irrigation, and b) to improve their water management policies and practices, especially in extreme conditions such as drought.

DIANA will use Earth Observation (EO) data and data from other sources, and implement state-of-the-art models. Through identifying legally, and illegally irrigated areas and estimating abstracted water volumes, **DIANA** will offer an affordable, cost-effective and added-value suite of data products and services.

DIANA consortium will deploy three pilots in order to test its services in real operational environments of Spain, Italy and Romania.

Objectives

- Define and create demand driven data products, services and pilot use cases
- Develop data products and design services based on EO data, as well as meteorological, surface and other supplementary data
- Design and integrate the service platform and its components to produce a fully operational and technically sound product
- Deploy and pilot the **DIANA** service platform in real operational environments integrated at the user level in order to openly demonstrate and validate the platform value
- Elaborate a tailored business plan for sustainable operation and market uptake beyond the end of the project

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Leadership in Enabling and Industrial Technologies - Space programme under grant agreement No. 731109 8 | 2

Fact Sheet
Detection and Integrated Assessment of Non-authorized water Abstractions using EO

Key Features

DIANA will leverage Earth Observation (EO) data and other data sources, as well as state-of-the-art models in order to offer the following affordable and cost effective data products and services:

- Detecting non-authorized water abstraction and monitoring to optimize control
- Forecasting and monitoring seasonal drought
- Assisting the implementation and monitoring of the Water Framework Directive (WFD)

DIANA services will be delivered through a web and mobile interface, both of which will be designed so as to be easily comprehensible and conceivable for all the potential users.

Benefits

DIANA will develop a set of advanced services, based on added value EO data, and will upgrade these services into a complete and qualified product with promising commercialisation potential. These services will enable users to harness the benefits and exploit the high potential of EO so as to achieve cost reductions, as well as optimisation of workflow and decision-making.

Project Coordinator

Agroapps PC, Greece

Project Partners

Administration Apelle Romania, Romania			
reco			
reco			

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Leadership in Enabling and Industrial Technologies - Space programme under grant agreement No. 731109 DIANA 2 | 3

ANNEX II: Targeted external non-project events

Event	Short Description	Link
Salon des maires et des collectivites locales 2017	Exhibition dedicated to Mayors and Local Authorities - the great French meeting for public procurement	http://www.salondesmaires.com/
World efficiency 2017	Expo & congress for Climate & Ressources. The World Efficiency show is an exhibition of solutions allowing professionals to preserve resource (saving, optimization and diversification solutions) and reduce greenhouse gas emissions (low carbon solutions)	https://www.world-efficiency.com/en/Home/
HYDROGAÏA	Water Conference and Trade Exhibition	http://www.hydrogaia-expo.com/
IFAT	International Trade Fair for Environment, Waste Water and Waste Disposal	http://www.ifat.de/index-2.html
ABWASSER.PRAXIS	Congress with trade fair dedicated exclusively to the topic of wastewater	http://www.abwasserpraxis.de/
2017 Irrigation Show & Education Conference	The Irrigation Show and Education Conference is where the irrigation industry comes together to network and learn	http://www.irrigation.org/irrigationshow/
AQUATECH AMSTERDAM	International Trade Exhibition of Water Technology and Water Management	http://www.eventseye.com/fairs/f-aquatech-amsterdam-122-1.html
SIGA	Spain's International Water Industry Fair. For Innovative Water Management Solutions	http://www.ifema.es/siga_06
AGWATEC SPAIN	International Agriculture & Water Technology Exhibition & Conference	http://agwatec.es/
EXPO ALCADIA	Show of Equipment and Services for Municipalities and Territorial Entities	http://www.feriazaragoza.com/events
SMAGUA	International Water Exhibition	http://www.smagua.com/

